

THE COMPLEXITIES AND STRATEGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN A MULTILINGUAL CLASSROOM

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the complexities encountered by teachers in teaching English in multilingual classrooms and the strategies they employ to address them in selected schools in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan. Using a descriptive research design, the study involved 73 English teachers from elementary, junior high school, and senior high school levels representing small, medium, large, and mega schools. Data were gathered through a survey questionnaire and analyzed using frequency and percentage, weighted mean, analysis of variance, and Pearson r correlation. Findings revealed that teachers strongly agreed that multilingual classrooms present considerable complexities, with learners' interest and motivation emerging as the most serious concern, followed by parental involvement, learners' proficiency, and teaching resources, while communication skills were rated as less severe though still challenging. In response, teachers consistently employed translation, code-switching, and feedback, whereas collaboration was used less frequently. Significant differences were found in the complexities encountered when respondents were grouped according to sex, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, grade level handled, and school size. The relationship analysis further showed that collaboration was significantly related to communication skills and teaching resources, while translation and feedback were significantly related to learners' proficiency. No strategy, however, showed a significant relationship with learners' interest and motivation or parental involvement. The study concludes that teaching English in multilingual classrooms demands flexible, context-sensitive strategies and sustained support for teachers to improve learner engagement, proficiency development, and inclusive classroom practice across diverse linguistic backgrounds, grade levels, and varied school contexts overall.

Keywords: *Multilingual classroom, English language teaching, teaching complexities, instructional strategies, learner proficiency*

INTRODUCTION

English, as a major medium of instruction and a core language of learning in Philippine basic education, plays a critical role in knowledge acquisition and dissemination. In the Philippines, where many learners use languages other than English at home, teaching English remains essential but also challenging. Many Filipino learners continue to experience difficulty using English confidently in authentic communication, even when they are exposed to it in school, which places continuing pressure on teachers to adopt effective strategies that can improve instruction and learning outcomes (Department of Education [DepEd], 2025; Leaño et al., 2019; Maramag-Manalastas & Batang, 2018).

Teaching English has become more difficult because of the rise of multilingual classrooms, where learners come from diverse linguistic backgrounds and possess varying levels of English competence. In the researcher's context in the City of Ilagan, Isabela, learners come from different language backgrounds and speak local languages such as Ilocano, Tagalog, and Ibanag at home and even with peers in school. This linguistic diversity poses significant complexities for English teachers because learners do not always share a common first language, and differences in prior language exposure, classroom participation, and cultural experiences can further complicate instruction. In such settings, multilingualism can be both a challenge and a resource, depending on how teachers respond pedagogically (De Los Reyes & Bagona, 2024; DepEd, 2025; Krulatz et al., 2023).

At San Rafael National and Vocational High School, this challenge is further compounded by the fact that learners speak different native languages, making it difficult for many of them to fully express themselves in English. Many learners struggle to compose sentences, articulate their ideas, and participate actively in discussions, and they often lack the confidence needed to communicate effectively in both academic and real-life situations. In multilingual English classrooms, speaking is frequently one of the weakest areas for learners, especially when vocabulary, oral fluency, and confidence are still developing. In some cases, learners ask their teachers to explain lessons in a language they know better, but this may also reduce their opportunities to practice English, which remains necessary in English instruction (Emperador-Garnace, 2021; Leaño et al., 2019; Maramag-Manalastas & Batang, 2018).

In these diverse learning situations, teachers must manage learners with varying linguistic backgrounds and proficiency levels, guide classroom interaction, and address cultural differences in ways that still promote English development. To respond to these complexities, teachers may employ a range of strategies such as using visual aids, adapting lesson plans to learners' needs, providing individualized support, and creating an inclusive classroom environment. Research has shown that visual aids and multimedia can improve learner engagement and comprehension, especially when paired with

individualized instruction, while multilingual classroom approaches such as scaffolding and translanguaging can help learners participate more meaningfully in class (DepEd, 2025; Halwani, 2017; Krulatz et al., 2023).

Given these circumstances, the researcher recognizes the importance of conducting a comprehensive study to explore the complexities encountered by teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom and the strategies they employ to address these complexities effectively. The goal of this research is to provide comprehensive information that would help English language instruction continue to advance, especially in classrooms with diverse and multilingual classroom.

Research Questions

This study sought to find out the complexities encountered by the teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom and the strategies employed to address these. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following problems:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Sex
 - b. Age
 - c. Highest Educational Attainment
 - d. Length of Service
 - e. Grade Level Handled
 - f. School Size
2. What are the complexities encountered by the respondents in teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom in terms of:
 - a. Learners' Interest and Motivation
 - b. Communication Skills
 - c. Learners' Proficiency
 - d. Teaching Resources
 - e. Parental Involvement
3. What strategies do the respondents employ to address the complexities in teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom in terms of:
 - a. Code-switching
 - b. Translation
 - c. Feedback
 - d. Collaboration
4. Is there significant difference in the complexities encountered by the teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom when grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there significant relationship between the complexities encountered and strategies employed in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive research design to identify the complexities and strategies in teaching English in a multilingual classroom. According to Sousa (2014), descriptive research design describes variables and the relationships that naturally exist between and among them. The descriptive research design was chosen for this study because it aimed to describe the respondents' profile, the level of complexities they faced, and the strategies employed in teaching English in a multilingual classroom. Additionally, the study sought to determine the relationship between the complexities and strategies employed. Therefore, this research design was considered the most appropriate to achieve the study's main objective.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in selected schools of School's Division City of Ilagan that are belong to the small, medium, large, and mega large size categories. The selected schools are San Pedro Integrated School and Sindun Bayabo Integrated School for the small category; San Antonio Elementary School and Lupigue Integrated School for the medium category; San Antonio National Agro-Industrial and Vocational High School and Rang Ayan National and Vocational High School for the large category; and Isabela School of Arts and Trade and Ilagan West Central School for the mega large category.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of the study were teachers from eight selected schools in the Schools Divisions of the City of Ilagan. The researcher employed a random selection technique, specifically a lottery method, to choose two schools from each of the school size category namely small, medium, large, and mega. The respondents consisted of teachers who instructed English to Grade 3-6 students in elementary, high school, and senior high school levels. In total, 73 teachers were selected as participants in the study.

Table 1
Respondents of the Study

Name of School	Number of Respondents
1. San Pedro Integrated School	8
2. Sindun Bayabo Integrated School	9
3. Lupigue Integrated School	11
4. San Antonio Elementary School	12
5. San Antonio National-Agro Industrial and Vocational High School	4
6. Rang-Ayan National and Vocational High School	4
7. Isabela School of Arts and Trade-Main Campus	13
8. Ilagan East Central School	12
Total	73

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers first sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan to conduct the study through official channels. Once permission was granted, the researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents in coordination with their respective school heads. The researcher ensured compliance with the Data Privacy Act regarding the respondents' profiles and questionnaire responses. After the questionnaires were completed, the researcher collected, analyzed, and interpreted the data.

Statistical Treatment of Data

After collecting the data, the researcher analyzed them using statistical tools, including frequency and percentage, weighted mean, ANOVA, and Pearson r correlation.

Frequency and Percentage Count were used to determine the respondents' profiles.

Weighted Mean was utilized to determine the complexities and strategies encountered by the respondents in teaching English in a multilingual classroom.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to ascertain significant differences in the complexities encountered and strategies employed by the respondents when grouped according to their profiles.

Pearson r was used to determine the significant relationship between the complexities and strategies used by respondents in teaching English in a multilingual classroom.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. **What is the Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of:**
 - a. **Sex**

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents as to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	16	21.91
Female	57	78.09
Total	73	100

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of their sex.

The data reveal that 57 or 78.09 percent of the respondents are females and 16 or 21.91 percent of them are males. This means that majority of the participants are females. It implies that the teaching force in the study area is largely dominated by women. The findings are supported by the study conducted by Riddell and Tett (2018), which analyzed the gender balance in teaching and examined the reasons behind the decline in the number and proportion of men in the profession, particularly in secondary schools. The study pointed that, similar to trends observed in developed countries such as Australia, the USA, and Canada, the number of men entering teaching has decreased significantly over a ten-year period. It also emphasized that as women's participation in paid work has increased, they have become more concentrated in service-oriented and caring professions like teaching.

b. Age

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents as to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Early Adulthood (22-34 years old)	31	42.47
Early Middle Age (35-44 years old)	35	47.94
Late Middle Age (45-64 years old)	7	9.59
Total	73	100

Table 3 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents as to their age. The data reveal that 35 or 47.94 percent of the respondents are 35-44 years old; 31 or 42.47 percent of them are 22-34 years old and seven or 9.59 percent of them are 45-64 years old. This means that most of the respondents are in the Early-Middle Age group.

The findings align with Raemdonck, et.al.'s (2022) study, which examined the impact of age on employability in education. The study found that the **middle-age group dominates the teaching workforce**, identifying complexities related to an aging staff and the need for innovation.

c. Highest Educational Attainment

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents as to Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor's Degree	14	19.18
With units in Master's Degree	31	42.47
Master's Degree	20	27.40
With Doctorate Units	6	8.22
Doctorate Degree	2	2.73
Total	73	100

Table 4 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of their highest educational attainment. The data reveal that Bachelor's Degree with units in Master's Degree has the highest frequency of 31 or 42.47 percent of the total population, while the Doctorate Degree category has the lowest frequency of two or 2.73 percent.

This means that most of the respondents have units in Master's Degree. It implies that most respondents have pursued higher education for professional growth, but only a few have attained a Doctorate degree.

The findings are supported by the study of Teves and Ubayubay's (2024) which looked into the role of self-motivation in teachers' professional growth and overall job satisfaction. The study revealed that obtaining a master's degree enhances leadership skills and mentoring capabilities, ultimately influencing the education sector. Most teachers are still pursuing their units in a master's degree, reflecting their commitment to professional development.

d. Length of Service

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents as to Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
1-3 years	28	38.36
4-6 years	23	31.51
7-9 years	16	21.91
10 years and above	6	8.22
Total	73	100

Table 5 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of their length of service. The data reveal that **respondents with 1-3 years of service have the highest frequency of 28 or 38.36 percent**, while **respondents with 10 and above years of service have the lowest frequency of six or 8.22 percent**. There are also 23 or 31.51 respondents who have served for 4-6 years and 16 or 21.91 percent respondents who have served for 7-9 years.

It implies that the teaching workforce in the study area is largely composed of early-career educators in the DepEd service. The distribution indicates a varied range of experience levels. A significant portion of the total population is relatively new to the organization, while other have earned more extensive service duration.

The findings above are similar to the study of Gagnon and Mattingly (2012), which identified that novice teachers, particularly those in their first or second year. This aligns with the present study's results, which indicate that the majority of the teaching workforce in the study area consists of early-career educators with 1-3 years of service, while those with extensive teaching experience (10 or more years) represent the smallest group.

e. Grade Level Handled

Table 6
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents as to Grade Level Handled

Grade Level Handled	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary	21	28.77
Junior High School	30	41.09
Senior High School	22	30.14
Total	73	100

Table 6 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of the grade level handled. The data reveal that 21 or 28.77 percent of the respondents handle elementary grades, 30 or 41.09 percent of them handle Junior High School and 22 or 30.14 percent of them handle Senior High School. This means that most of the respondents are teachers of grades 7,8, 9, and 10.

The findings are aligned with the study by Ingersoll and Seven (2013), *where it had been found* that teacher distribution varies across different education levels, with a notable concentration of educators in the middle-grade levels, particularly in Junior High School. This trend is influenced by factors such as student enrollment patterns, subject specialization requirements, and staffing allocations in schools.

f. School Size

Table 7
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents as to School Size

School Size	Frequency	Percentage
Small	17	23.29
Medium	23	31.51
Large	8	10.96
Mega	25	34.25
Total	73	100

Table 7 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of school size. The data reveal that 17 or 23.29 percent of the respondents are in small school size, 23 or 31.51 percent of them are in medium school size, eight or 10.96 percent of them are in large school size, 25 or 34.25 percent of them are in mega-large school size.

According to DepEd Memorandum No. 43 s. 2017, in elementary schools, a **small** school has **289 students and below**, a **medium** school has **290–841 students**, a **large** school has **842–1,450 students**, and a **mega** school has **1,451 students and above**. For junior high schools, a **small** school has **399 students and below**, a **medium** school has **400–750 students**, a **large** school has **751–1,250 students**, and **mega** school has

1,251 students and above. Meanwhile, senior high schools are classified as **small** if they have **less than 440 students**, **medium** with **441–840 students**, **large** with **841–1,240 students**, and **mega** with **1,241 students and above**. These classifications help in planning school resources, staffing, and facilities to ensure effective educational service delivery. On the other hand, integrated schools are categorized based on the number of teachers they have. A small school consists of 9 or fewer teachers in elementary or 15 or fewer in secondary. A medium school has 10 to 29 teachers in elementary or 16 to 30 in secondary. A large school includes 30 to 50 teachers in elementary or 31 to 50 in secondary. Lastly, a mega school consists of 51 or more teachers, whether in elementary or secondary education.

2. **What are the Level of Complexities encountered by the respondents in teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom in terms of:**
 - a. **Learners’ Interest and Motivation**

Table 8
Complexities of Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom as to Learners’ Interest and Motivation

Learners’ Interest and Motivation	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Learners feel uncomfortable when required to speak English in class.	3.44	Strongly Agree
2. Learners struggle to stay on task due to difficulties in understanding instructions, leading to distractions.	3.16	Agree
3. Learners’ expressions of unease with direct English instruction show motivation when code-switching is utilized.	3.33	Strongly Agree
4. Learners find it challenging to articulate their thoughts in the English language.	3.40	Strongly Agree
5. Learners exhibit boredom during story time, often stemming from a lack of comprehension.	3.30	Strongly Agree
Average Mean Value	3.33	Strongly Agree

Table 8 displays the complexities of teaching English in a multilingual classroom in terms of learners’ interest and motivation. The data reveal that *Learners feel uncomfortable when required to speak English in class*, *Learners’ expressions of unease with direct English instruction show motivation when code-switching is utilized*, *Learners find it challenging to articulate their thoughts in the English language*, and *Learners exhibit boredom during story time, often stemming from a lack of comprehension* have higher means of 3.44, 3.33, 3.40, and 3.30, respectively, all with a qualitative description of **Strongly Agree**. Meanwhile, *Learners struggle to stay on task due to difficulties in understanding instructions, leading to distractions* has a mean of 3.16, with a qualitative description of **Agree**.

This indicates that the respondents agree to strongly agree that learners’ interest and motivation are complexities in teaching English in a multilingual classroom.

These findings are supported by the study of Gambhir-Bahadur (2024) who have identified the complexities learners face while speaking in English, based on responses from 15 participants through questionnaires and interviews. Nearly 20 issues were identified and categorized into personal, linguistic, social, and environmental problems. Key challenges included nervousness, lack of confidence, limited vocabulary, difficulty with grammatical patterns, pronunciation issues, fear of making mistakes, overreliance on their mother tongue, and insufficient exposure to English. Personal and linguistic issues were the most prominent, exacerbated by social fears and environmental barriers.

b. Communication Skills

Table 9
Complexities of Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom as to Communication Skills

Communication Skills	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Communicating with learners is difficult due to the absence of a common first language.	2.70	Agree
2. It difficult to understand the learners' pronunciation.	2.70	Agree
3. It is difficult to determine the language to use because of the presence of multiple languages.	2.78	Agree
4. Learners struggle to express themselves adequately, resulting in frequent misunderstandings.	3.14	Agree
5. It is difficult to comprehend the messages learners attempt to convey.	2.77	Agree
Average Mean Value	2.82	Agree

Table 9 shows the complexities encountered by teachers in teaching English in multilingual classrooms in relation to communication skills. The data reveal that *Learner's struggle to express themselves adequately, resulting in frequent misunderstandings* has the highest mean score of 3.14 with a qualitative description of **Agree**. Meanwhile, *Communicating with learners is difficult due to the absence of a common first language* and *It is difficult to understand the learners' pronunciation* with a mean score of 2.70 and a qualitative description of **Agree** are the lowest in mean scores.

The results suggest that the absence of a common first language, varied pronunciations, and the presence of multiple languages hinder effective communication between teachers and learners. This impacts learners' ability to express themselves and the teacher's ability to comprehend the messages conveyed by learners. Hence, these complexities disrupt classroom interactions and may affect student engagement and learning.

This affirms the study of Defino (2019) who explored the impact of language processing challenges on student engagement and academic performance in a multilingual setting. He found that difficulties in perception, processing, and expression of language significantly hindered their ability to articulate ideas clearly. These

complexities led to frequent misunderstandings and negatively affected classroom participation. Pronunciation issues, limited vocabulary, and anxiety were the most common barriers, causing learners to shy away from active engagement. As a result, their academic performance suffered compared to peers with better communication skills.

c. Learners’ Proficiency

Table 10
Complexities of Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom as to Learner’s Proficiency

Learners’ Proficiency	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Learners consistently demonstrate various grammatical and pronunciation errors.	3.15	Agree
2. Learners’ comprehension of English, especially vocabulary, is insufficient for effective learning.	3.28	Strongly Agree
3. Learners’ verbal expression is limited, both in general terms and in specific aspects.	3.34	Strongly Agree
4. Learners resort to gestures and mixing languages because of limited English vocabulary.	3.23	Strongly Agree
5. Learners struggle with oral tasks.	3.37	Strongly Agree
Average Mean Value	3.27	Strongly Agree

Table 10 presents the complexities encountered by teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom focusing on learners' proficiency. The data reveal that *Learners’ comprehension of English, especially vocabulary, is insufficient for effective learning, Learners’ verbal expression is limited, both in general terms and in specific aspects, Learners resort to gestures and mixing languages because of limited English vocabulary, and Learners struggle with oral tasks* have higher means of 3.28, 3.34, 3.23, and 3.37, respectively, all with a qualitative description of **Strongly Agree**. Meanwhile, *Learners consistently demonstrate various grammatical and pronunciation errors* has a mean of 3.15, with a qualitative description of **Agree**. This means that the respondents agree to strongly agree that learner’s proficiency is a complexity in teaching English in a multilingual classroom.

The findings from Table 8 are supported by the study of Jaekel et al. (2023), which identified that learners struggle with oral tasks due to nervousness about making mistakes and limited vocabulary, making it difficult for them to express their thoughts effectively. Shohamy (2006) details the difficulties teachers encounter in managing these language barriers, while Dincer (2018) examines the correlation between vocabulary proficiency and effective student engagement. Further, Umrani and Lohar (2015) explore adaptive strategies like code-switching and using gestures due to limited vocabulary, corroborating issues of verbal expression and language mixing. Additionally, Jaekel et al. (2023) points out the challenges with oral tasks and advocates for targeted support to enhance verbal skills, aligning with the high agreement on learners' struggles with oral tasks.

d. Teaching Resources

Table 11
Complexities of Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom as to Teaching Resources

Teaching Resources	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. There is lack of appropriate materials in textbooks that accommodate language differences.	3.21	Agree
2. Teacher training is limited if not lacking, leading to unpreparedness in instructing multilingual learners.	3.25	Strongly Agree
3. There is scarcity of materials for language lessons tailored to multilingual learners.	3.27	Strongly Agree
4. There is lack of evaluation materials to assess the language needs of multilingual learners.	3.25	Strongly Agree
5. It is difficult to select suitable content for multilingual learners.	3.33	Strongly Agree
Average Mean Value	3.26	Strongly Agree

Table 11 presents the complexities encountered by teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom focusing on teaching resources. The data reveal that *Teacher training is limited if not lacking, leading to unpreparedness in instructing multilingual learners, There is scarcity of materials for language lessons tailored to multilingual learners, There is lack of evaluation materials to assess the language needs of multilingual learners, and It is difficult to select suitable content for multilingual learners* have higher means of 3.25, 3.27, 3.25, and 3.33, respectively, with a qualitative description of **Strongly Agree**. Meanwhile, *There is lack of appropriate materials in textbooks that accommodate language differences* has a mean of 3.21, with a qualitative description of Agree.

This indicates that the respondents agree to strongly agree that teaching resources is a complexity in teaching English in a Multilingual classroom.

The findings align with a study conducted by Lestariningsih and Darmawan (2023) at South Woods Middle School (SWMS) in the Syosset School District focused on this critical issue, emphasizing the lack of essential materials and support systems necessary for creating an inclusive learning environment for English Language Learner (ELL) and bilingual learners. The research identified factors such as limited access to resources and a shortage of ongoing support for teachers, which hinder effective instruction.

e. Parental Involvement

Table 12
Complexities of Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom as to Parental Involvement

Parental Involvement	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Parents who do not speak English at home are unable to support English language development.	4.25	Strongly Agree
2. Interacting with parents is difficult due to language and cultural differences.	3.00	Agree
3. Parents are unwilling to actively support English language development.	2.25	Disagree
4. Parents are unable to support their children in their homework.	3.75	Strongly Agree
5. Parents perceive learners' English language development as solely the school's responsibility.	3.12	Agree
Average Mean Value	3.28	Strongly Agree

Table 12 presents the complexities of teaching English in a multilingual classroom with regard to parental involvement. *Parents who do not speak English at home are unable to support English language development* has the highest mean of 4.25 with a qualitative description of **Strongly Agree**. Meanwhile, *Parents are unwilling to actively support English language development* has the lowest mean with a qualitative description of Disagree.

This implies that parents who do not speak English at home are unable to support their children's English language development, but they are willing to support their children despite their limitations. The findings above are similar to the study by Gachari et al. (2023) which explored the challenges of parental involvement in the education of immigrant learners. The study found that while parents are important for their children's education, their ability to support language development is limited if they do not speak the language being learned.

Table 13
Summary of the Complexities Encountered by Teacher in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom

Complexities	Average Mean Value	Qualitative Description
Learners' Interest and Motivation	3.33	Strongly Agree
Communication Skills	2.82	Agree
Learners' Proficiency	3.27	Strongly Agree
Teaching Resources	3.26	Strongly Agree
Parental Involvement	3.28	Strongly Agree
Total Average Mean Value	3.20	Strongly Agree

Table 13 shows the summary table of complexities encountered by teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom. Among the complexities, learners' interest and motivation have the highest average mean value of 3.33, interpreted as **Strongly Agree**. This is followed closely by parental involvement, with an average mean value of 3.28, also interpreted as **Strongly Agree**, and learners' proficiency, with an average mean value of 3.27, also described as **Strongly Agree**. Teaching resources follow with an average mean value of 3.26, also interpreted as **Strongly Agree**. However, communication skills have the lowest average weighted mean of 2.82, interpreted as **Agree**.

The results imply that motivating learners, engaging parents, ensuring learner proficiency, and providing adequate teaching resources are key to improving education in a multilingual classroom. It also indicates that **existing communication strategies and tools are already effective** which means that teachers and learners are able to convey and understand the lessons without significant complexities.

The findings aligned to the study by Razi and Rahmat (2020) which investigated the motivation levels of English language learners and the strategies employed by teachers to support this motivation. Findings revealed that while most students exhibited a relatively high level of motivation, a few in almost every class showed a lack of motivation. Furthermore, Yusob (2018) identified the challenges faced by teachers when teaching grammar at the undergraduate level in his study on the challenges of teaching grammar in Malaysia. Results suggest that lecturers encountered six problems: the lack of expertise of lecturers in teaching grammar, students poor or weak competency, lack of resources, teachers' unfavorable opinions on the teaching of grammar, and preparation of grammar classes.

3. What Strategies do the respondents employ to address the complexities in teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom in terms of:
a. Code-Switching

Table 14
Strategies to Address the Complexities in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom as to Code-Switching

Code-switching	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. I use code-switching to facilitate the language learning process in my diverse classroom.	3.27	Always
2. I incorporate code-switching as an integral component of the English lesson, addressing multilingual dynamics.	3.37	Always
3. I employ code-switching as a strategic and efficient technique, enhancing my teaching approach in a multilingual setting.	3.26	Always
4. I resort to code-switching judiciously, considering it a valuable resource only when all other instructional options have been explored.	3.27	Always

5. I am aware of the potential effects, recognizing that the practice of code-switching may influence learners' reliance and dependency on me as their teacher in a multilingual learning environment.	3.44	Always
Average Mean Value	3.32	Always

Table 14 provides the strategies employed by the respondents in addressing the complexities of teaching English in a multilingual classroom on code-switching. The data reveal that *I am aware of the potential effects, recognizing that the practice of code-switching may influence learners' reliance and dependency on me as their teacher in a multilingual learning environment* has the highest mean of 3.44, interpreted as **Always**. On the other hand, *I employ code-switching as a strategic and efficient technique, enhancing my teaching approach in a multilingual setting* has the lowest mean of 3.26, also interpreted as **Always**.

This means that the teacher-respondents consistently use code-switching in their classroom to address language barriers and improve learning, though they are aware of its potential impact on learners' dependence.

The findings align with the studies of Makalela (2015) and Bravo-Sotelo (2020), which focus on the advantages of code-switching and translanguaging in multilingual classrooms. Makalela research demonstrated that these strategies not only fostered multi-competence in teachers but also enhanced learners' comprehension of content. Similarly, Bravo-Sotelo's research on Tagalog-English code-switching reinforced this idea, emphasizing that while these practices improve understanding, they may inadvertently increase learners' dependence on the teacher for further clarification. However, both studies noted that such strategies could foster learners' reliance and dependency on their teachers, as learners might depend on their guidance to navigate between languages, potentially limiting their independent language acquisition and critical thinking.

b. Translation

Table 15
Strategies to Address the Complexities in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom as to Translation

Translation	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. I allow learners to look up the English-Filipino dictionary for each new word.	3.16	Frequently
2. I sometimes translate English sentences into the languages they use.	3.40	Always
3. I allow learners to use their language in expressing their thoughts in my class.	3.30	Always
4. I find that translation assists learners in analyzing and interpreting a source text.	3.36	Always

5. I translate the lesson in the learners' language because it contributes to a better-quality output in my teaching.	3.56	Always
Average Mean Value	3.36	Always

Table 15 displays the strategies employed by the respondents in addressing the complexities of teaching English in a multilingual classroom as to translation. The data reveal that *I translate the lesson in the learners' language because it contributes to a better-quality output in my teaching* has the highest mean of 3.56 interpreted as **Always**, while *I allow learners to look up the English-Filipino dictionary for each new word* has the lowest mean of 3.16 interpreted as **Frequently**.

This means that most teacher-respondents use translation as a tool in teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom, with a strong emphasis on translating lessons into learners' language to enhance teaching quality. The use of English-Tagalog dictionary to learn meaning of new word is also employed.

The findings are aligned with the research conducted by Arfianti and Widiati (2020) at Universitas Negeri Malang, where it had been found that learners perceive translation positively in enhancing their English learning experience. The study also pointed out various learning activities involving translation that effectively support comprehension and engagement.

c. Feedback

Table 16
Strategies to Address the Complexities in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom as to Feedback

Feedback	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. I encourage my learners to give feedback on their classmates' work.	3.16	Frequently
2. I provide criticism if the learners' thoughts are not related.	3.26	Always
3. I engage in discussions with learners about their performance and offer advice on improvement.	3.29	Always
4. I encourage peer feedback using learners' first language in my class.	3.34	Always
5. I acknowledge learners when they achieve something in my teaching.	3.33	Always
Average Mean Value	3.28	Always

Table 16 presents the strategies employed by the respondents in addressing the complexities of teaching English in a multilingual classroom as to feedback. The data reveal that *I encourage peer feedback using their first language in my class* has the highest mean of 3.34 interpreted as **Always**, while *I encourage my learners to give feedback on their classmates' work* has the lowest mean of 3.16 interpreted as **Frequently**.

This means that the teacher-respondents utilize feedback strategy in class with much focus on encouraging peer feedback using learners' first language in 'first language and also with acknowledging achievements, discussions about performance and giving advice for improvement and criticism when necessary. The findings above are aligned with the findings of Herra and Kulińska (2018) on the use of peer feedback in language learning in multilingual classrooms. Their study emphasized that peer feedback, particularly when conducted in learners' first language, can enhance learners' understanding and engagement with the material. It was found that learners were more comfortable and open to providing feedback in their native language, which fostered a collaborative learning environment and improved language development.

d. Collaboration

Table 17
Strategies to Address the Complexities in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom as to Collaboration

Collaboration	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. I instruct learners to pronounce words and then ask their classmates to imitate them.	2.89	Frequently
2. I promote think-pair-share activities using the English language only.	2.56	Frequently
3. I encourage the promotion of peer-assisted strategies if learners do not understand English instructions.	2.60	Frequently
4. I facilitate small group discussions for sharing ideas and thoughts.	2.59	Frequently
5. I organize a problem and group learners to solve a topic-related problem to enhance their English proficiency.	2.60	Frequently
Average Mean Value	2.65	Frequently

Table 17 gives the strategies employed by the respondents in addressing the complexities of teaching English in a multilingual classroom on collaboration. The data reveal that *I instruct learners to pronounce words and then ask their classmates to imitate them* has the highest mean of 2.89 interpreted as **Frequently**, while *I promote think-pair-share activities using the English language only* has the lowest mean of 2.56 also interpreted as **Frequently**.

This means that most teacher-respondents frequently use collaborative strategies, mostly involving student pronunciation exercises and peer imitation that support language learning. The findings above are similar to the study by Awad (2017) at the ELC An-Najah National University, where researchers interviewed EFL teachers and observed learners' classroom interactions. Specifically, the think-pair-share strategy was found to play a positive role in improving learners' oral communicative skills, creating a cooperative learning environment, and enhancing motivation to learn better. Similarly, the present study points that teacher frequently use collaborative strategies, such as student

pronunciation exercises and peer imitation, to support language learning, although the exclusive use of English in such activities may not always be consistent.

Table 18
Summary of Strategies Employed by the Respondents to Address the Complexities in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom

Strategies	Average Mean Value	Qualitative Description
Code-switching	3.32	Always
Translation	3.36	Always
Feedback	3.28	Always
Collaboration	2.65	Frequently
Total Average Mean Value	3.15	Frequently

Table 18 presents the summary table of strategies employed by respondents to address the complexities in teaching English in a multilingual classroom. Among the strategies, Translation has the highest average mean value of 3.36 interpreted as **Always**. This is followed closely by Code-switching with an average weighted mean of 3.32 and Feedback with an average weighted mean of 3.28 both interpreted as **Always**. However, Collaboration, with an average weighted mean of 2.65 is interpreted as **Frequently**. Overall, the results imply a strong reliance on direct instructional strategies, as the first three strategies involve explicit teaching, teacher-led discussions, and guided practice, which are key features of direct instruction. Meanwhile, collaborative approaches are less emphasized.

The results imply that respondents prefer strategies like code-switching, translation, and feedback, which provide immediate and direct support to learners in overcoming language barriers in multilingual classrooms. This preference may reflect the effectiveness and ease of these strategies in ensuring comprehension and addressing proficiency gaps. However, the less consistent use of collaboration suggests that teachers may face complexities in implementing this strategy, possibly due to time constraints, lack of training, or the complexity of managing group dynamics.

The result is similar to the study carried out by Cahyani et al. (2018). The results showed that educators used five different kinds of communication strategies: literal translation, code-switching, nonverbal cues, fillers and hesitation-gambits, repeating of oneself and others, and requests for assistance. The outcomes show that implementing these strategies helps raise learners' achievement levels and performance in the classroom. Furthermore, there are two categories of feedback that educators employ in the teaching and learning process: oral and visual feedback. Both of the studies suggest that direct instructional strategies, such as translation, code-switching, and feedback, are effective in multilingual classrooms, reinforcing their importance in ensuring comprehension and improving student performance.

4. Is there significant difference in the complexities encountered by the teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom when grouped according to their profile?

a. Learners' Interest and Motivation

Table 19
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Complexities in Terms of Learners' Interest and Motivation Encountered by the Teachers in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom When Grouped According to their Profile

Teacher's Complexities in Learners' Interest and Motivation and the following Profile	Probability of F	Remarks
Sex	0.0016	Significant
Age	5.88E-05	Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	5.00E-08	Significant
Length of Service	9.78E-07	Significant
Grade Level Handled	0.0012	Significant
School Size	4.18E-11	Significant

Table 19 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the complexities encountered by teachers regarding learners' interest and motivation when teaching English in a multilingual classroom, grouped by profile. The results indicate that the F-probability values are less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 0.05 significance level. This suggests a significant difference in complexities to learners' interest and motivation encountered by teachers when grouped according to their profile. It implies that teachers vary from each other in complexities they encounter on learners' interest and motivation in teaching English in a multilingual classroom, depending on factors such as sex, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, grade level handled, and school size.

It is further inferred that female teachers in early adulthood, holding a doctoral degree, with 1-3 and 7-9 years of service, handling elementary grades, and teaching in mega size school encounter more complexities in learners' interest and motivation in teaching English in a multilingual classroom. This is evidenced by their highest means of 3.39, 3.43, 3.60, 3.41, 3.57, and 3.33 respectively. These findings suggest that various aspects of a teacher's profile significantly influence their effectiveness in engaging and motivating learners in a multilingual classroom.

This aligns with the research by Jensen et al. (2020), which found that younger teachers often employ more dynamic and interactive strategies due to their familiarity with digital technologies, which can differ significantly from the approaches used by more experienced teachers. Conversely, older teachers might rely more on traditional methods but possess refined classroom management skills that can also effectively enhance student motivation. Additionally, the study by Castilla-Earls and Ericks-Brophy (2018) supports the idea that teachers' educational backgrounds can equip them with varying pedagogical skills and knowledge, influencing their motivational techniques.

b. Communication Skills

Table 20
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Complexities Encountered by the Teachers in terms of Communication Skills in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom when Grouped According to their Profile

Teacher's Complexities in Communication Skills and the following Profile	Probability of F	Remarks
Sex	0.0044	Significant
Age	0.0002	Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	1.29E-06	Significant
Length of Service	3.95E-05	Significant
Grade Level Handled	0.0003	Significant
School Size	1.83E-15	Significant

Table 20 shows the results of the test of significant difference in the complexities in terms of communication skills encountered by the teachers in teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom when grouped according to their profile. It is evident from the results that the probability values of F are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the complexities in communication skills encountered by the teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom when grouped according to their profile. It shows that the teachers encounter varied complexities on communication skills.

It further states that the teachers who are female, in their early adulthood, with doctorate degree, in their service for 1-3 years and handling elementary level, and teaching in a mega size school met more complexities in teaching English in a multilingual classroom since they got the highest means of 2.92, 2.95, 3.20, 2.97, 2.94, and 2.82 respectively. These findings implies that teachers' effectiveness in overcoming communication barriers in multilingual settings is heavily influenced by their personal and professional characteristics.

Temelkovska (2023) discusses how gender influences communication styles, noting different interaction methods between male and female teachers that can affect efficacy in multilingual settings. Similarly, Cruickshank et al. (2012) find that younger teachers are more likely to adopt technology-enhanced communication methods, which aligns with the age-related differences observed. Munthe and Rogne (2015) suggest that higher educational levels equip teachers with advanced pedagogical skills that improve communication in diverse classrooms. Further, Liu, et.al. (2023), pointed out that more experienced teachers develop refined strategies for overcoming language barriers.

c. Learner’s Proficiency

Table 21
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Complexities Encountered by Teachers in terms of Learners’ Proficiency in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom When Grouped According to their Profile

Teacher’s Complexities in Learners’ Proficiency and the following Profile	Probability of F	Remarks
Sex	0.0012	Significant
Age	8.89-05	Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	1.4-06	Significant
Length of Service	9.55-06	Significant
Grade Level Handled	0.0026	Significant
School Size	1.02E-15	Significant

Table 21 displays the results of the test of significant difference in the complexities in terms of learners’ proficiency encountered by teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom. The results reveal that the F-probability values are less than 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the complexities regarding learners’ proficiency encountered by teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom when they are grouped according to their profile. This implies that the complexities in learners’ proficiency faced by teachers vary based on factors such as sex, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, grade level handled, and school size.

Furthermore, the data suggests that female teachers in the late middle age group, holding a doctoral degree, have taught for 10 years or more, handling elementary, and teaching in mega size school encounter more complexities regarding learners’ proficiency in teaching English in a multilingual classroom. This is evidenced by their respective higher means of 3.26, 3.46, 3.80, 3.44, 3.53, 3.67, and 3.27. This information suggests that personal and professional characteristics such as sex, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, grade level handled, and the school size significantly affect a teacher’s ability to effectively communicate in diverse classroom settings.

This is supported by the findings of Rasheed et al. (2017), whose study conducted in Quetta, Pakistan, explored the difficulties faced by female teachers in government secondary schools. The findings revealed that linguistic diversity in classrooms posed significant challenges, leading to students' reluctance to use English due to fear of making mistakes. Ortmann, et al. (2024) found in their study that experienced educators, particularly those with advanced degrees, may face unique challenges in adapting to diverse linguistic environments. Their extensive training often emphasizes traditional methodologies, which might not fully address the dynamic needs of multilingual classrooms. Lastly, Harris and Herrington (2015) identified in their study that mega schools introduce additional challenges, such as increased administrative duties and larger class sizes. These factors can impede personalized instruction, making it more difficult to address individual learner needs in multilingual classrooms.

d. Teaching Resources

Table 22
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Complexities Encountered by Teachers in terms of Teaching Resources in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom when Grouped According to their Profile

Teacher's Complexities in Teaching Resources and the following Profile	Probability of F	Remarks
Sex	0.0027	Significant
Age	0.0002	Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	9.29E-07	Significant
Length of Service	5.37E-06	Significant
Grade Level Handled	0.0002	Significant
School Size	1.58E-15	Significant

Table 22 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the complexities regarding teaching resources encountered by teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom, when grouped according to their profile. It is evident from the results that the probability values of F are less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, there is a significant difference in the complexities regarding teaching resources encountered by teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom, when grouped according to their profile.

This suggests that teachers differ from each other in the complexities they encounter with teaching resources when teaching English in a multilingual classroom, based on factors such as age, sex, highest educational attainment, length of service, grade level handled, and school size. Furthermore, it indicates that female teachers in the early adulthood age group, holding a doctoral degree, with 1-3 years of service, teaching at the junior high school level, and belong to mega school size encounter more complexities with teaching resources. This is supported by their higher means of 2.63, 2.68, 3.00, 2.70, 2.66, 2.71, and 3.26 respectively.

The findings are supported by the study of Erling et. al (2017), which examined the challenges faced by teachers in multilingual classrooms. The study found that linguistic diversity, varying levels of English proficiency, and inadequate teaching resources significantly impact the effectiveness of English language instruction. Additionally, it emphasized the need for well-structured teacher training programs and resource development to address these challenges.

e. Parental Involvement

Table 23
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Complexities Encountered by Teachers in Terms of Parental Involvement in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom when Grouped According to their Profile

Teacher's Complexities in Parental Involvement and the following Profile	Probability of F	Remarks
Sex	0.0036	Significant
Age	8.88E-05	Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	4.35E-07	Significant
Length of Service	1.56E-06	Significant
Grade Level Handled	2.00E-05	Significant
School Size	5.51E-15	Significant

Table 23 reveals the results of the test of significant differences in the complexities related to parental involvement encountered by teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom, grouped according to their profile. The results indicate that the F-probability values are less than 0.05, leading to the rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the complexities regarding parental involvement encountered by teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom when grouped according to their profile.

This suggests that teachers vary in the complexities they face regarding parental involvement when teaching English in a multilingual classroom, based on factors such as sex, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, grade level handled, and school size. Furthermore, it indicates that female teachers in the early middle adulthood age group, holding a bachelor's degree, with 1-3 years of service, teaching at the senior high school level, and belong to medium school size encounter more complexities in parental involvement when teaching English in a multilingual classroom, as evidenced by their higher means of 2.37, 2.39, 2.47, 2.39, 2.36, 2.31, and 3.28 respectively.

The study conducted by Housel (2020) aligns with these findings, emphasizing that parental involvement poses complexity in multilingual classrooms due to immigrant parents' intimidation, perceived language barriers, and unfamiliarity with American educational norms. These factors can hinder their engagement, impacting their children's educational experiences and opportunities for collaboration with school personnel.

5. Is there a significant relationship between the complexities encountered and strategies employed in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom?

a. Learners' Interest and Motivation

Table 24
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Complexities Encountered in Learners' Interest and Motivation and the Strategies Employed in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom

Complexities on Learners' Interest and Motivation and the following Strategies Employed in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom	Probability of r	Remarks
Code-switching	0.7241	Not Significant
Translation	0.2858	Not Significant
Feedback	0.3337	Not Significant
Collaboration	0.9818	Not Significant

The results of the test for significant relationship between the complexities encountered in learners' interest and motivation and the strategies employed in teaching English in a multilingual classroom are displayed in Table 24. It is evident from the results that the r-probability values are greater than 0.05. As a result, the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 significance level. As a result, there is no significant relationship between the complexities encountered in learners' interest and motivation and the strategies employed in teaching English in a multilingual classroom. This implies that the complexities met by teachers in learners' interest and motivation are not significantly affected by the strategies employed in teaching English in a multilingual classroom. Furthermore, it indicates that the two variables are not significantly related.

These findings are consistent with Wong (2014) which examined the Chinese EFL context. It has been found that while teachers employed various motivational strategies, there was limited empirical evidence to support their effectiveness in enhancing student motivation.

Conversely, other research suggests that teacher motivation and the use of motivating strategies can positively influence student motivation and achievement. For instance, a study by Bernaus, et al. (2009) in Catalonia, Spain, found that teacher motivation was related to the use of motivating strategies, which in turn were related to student motivation and English achievement. Similarly, Jones (2019) investigated EFL classrooms in Costa Rica and found strong positive correlations between student motivation and various aspects of teacher motivational practices, except for 'teacher discourse,' suggesting that excessive teacher talk may impede student motivation.

b. Communication Skills

Table 25
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Complexities Encountered in Communication Skills and the Strategies Employed in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom

Complexities on Communication Skills and the following Strategies Employed in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom	Probability of r	Remarks
Code-switching	0.8990	Not Significant
Translation	0.3968	Not Significant
Feedback	0.0573	Not Significant
Collaboration	0.0226	Significant

Table 25 presents the results of the test for significant relationship between the complexities encountered in communication skills and the strategies employed in teaching English in a multilingual classroom.

The results reveal that the probability values of r are greater than 0.05, except for collaboration. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 significance level. Thus, there is no significant relationship between the complexities encountered in communication skills and the strategies employed in teaching English in a multilingual classroom in terms of code-switching, translation, and feedback. This indicates that these three strategies used in teaching English in a multilingual classroom have no significant effect on the complexities encountered by teachers in communication skills.

However, there is a significant relationship between the complexities encountered in communication skills and the collaboration strategy employed in teaching English in a multilingual classroom. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 0.05 significance level. This implies that the collaboration strategy used by teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom significantly affects their complexities in communication skills.

The findings above are similar to the study by Mirbazei and Arjmandi (2018) which examined the impact of code-switching and translation strategies on Iranian EFL students' language learning. The results indicated that while these strategies enhanced language learning, they did not specifically address communication complexities. Additionally, a study by Ghorbani and Nezamoshari'e (2012) explored the use of collaborative learning techniques in EFL classrooms. The study found that collaboration among students significantly improved their communication skills.

On the other hand, a study by Littlewood and Yu (2011) suggested that code-switching can facilitate comprehension and communication in multilingual classrooms.

c. Learners' Proficiency

Table 26
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Complexities Encountered in Learners' Proficiency and the Strategies Employed in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom

Complexities on Learners' Proficiency and the following Strategies Employed in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom	Probability of r	Remarks
Code-switching	0.5752	Not Significant
Translation	0.0106	Significant
Feedback	0.0424	Significant
Collaboration	0.4688	Not Significant

The results of the test for significant relationship between the complexities encountered in learners' proficiency and the strategies employed in teaching English in a multilingual classroom are presented in Table 26. It is evident from the results that the P-values of r are less than 0.05, except for code-switching and collaboration. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the complexities encountered in learners' proficiency and the translation and feedback strategies employed in teaching English in a multilingual classroom. This indicates that these two strategies used by teachers significantly affect the complexities they encounter in learners' proficiency.

On the other hand, there is no significant relationship between the complexities encountered in learners' proficiency and the strategies of code-switching and collaboration employed in teaching English in a multilingual classroom. This suggests that the said strategies have no significant effect on the complexities encountered by teachers in learners' proficiency.

Mirbazel and Arjmandi (2018) examined the impact of translation strategies on Iranian EFL students' language learning. Their study revealed that incorporating translation alongside English instruction enhanced students' comprehension and language acquisition, supporting the significant relationship between translation strategies and learners' proficiency. Similarly, in the context of multilingual classrooms, where learners face challenges in proficiency due to varied linguistic backgrounds, the use of translation strategies can bridge comprehension gaps and facilitate learning. The significant relationship observed in this study supports the idea that translation plays a crucial role in helping multilingual learners overcome proficiency-related difficulties.

Meanwhile, Cahyani et al. (2023) explored teachers' code-switching in Indonesian bilingual classrooms. They found that code-switching served pedagogical functions, such as clarifying concepts and managing classroom interactions, which facilitated better comprehension and communication. Similarly, Sato and Viveros (2016) found that group dynamics play a crucial role in the success of collaborative tasks in foreign language

classrooms. Their study emphasized that factors such as group composition, individual learner roles, peer relationships, and task structure significantly influence the effectiveness of collaboration in language learning.

d. Teaching Resources

Table 27
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Complexities Encountered in Teaching Resources and the Strategies Employed in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom

Complexities on Teaching Resources and the following Strategies Employed in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom	Probability of r	Remarks
Code -switching	0.2589	Not Significant
Translation	0.2149	Not Significant
Feedback	0.5604	Not Significant
Collaboration	0.0144	Significant

Table 27 discloses the result of the test of significant relationships between the complexities encountered in teaching resources and the strategies employed in teaching English in multilingual classroom. The results reveal that the r-probability values are greater than 0.05, except for collaboration. For this reason, the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is no significant relationship between the complexities encountered in teaching resources and the strategies employed in teaching English in a multilingual classroom in terms of code-switching, translation, and feedback. It shows that the aforementioned strategies employed by the teachers when teaching English in a multilingual classroom do not significantly affect the complexities, they encounter in teaching resources.

However, there is a significant relationship between the complexities encountered in teaching resources and the collaboration strategy employed in teaching English in a multilingual classroom. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 0.05 significance level. It implies that the complexities encountered by the teachers in teaching resources are significantly affected by the collaboration strategy used by the teacher when they teach English in a multilingual classroom.

The present study negates the study by Gamelo and Roy (2024) as it investigates code-switching practices among junior high school teachers and learners in English as a Second Language (ESL) classes in the Philippines. The findings Gamelo and Roy revealed that both teachers and learners perceive code-switching as beneficial and necessary in ESL instruction, particularly in understanding lesson content, managing discipline and classroom behavior, and building relationships and engaging learners. However, unlike Gamelo and Roy’s findings, this study reveals that code-switching does not significantly impact teaching resource complexities. While their study identifies its benefits in instruction and engagement, the current findings suggest that resource-related challenges are better addressed through collaboration.

e. Parental Involvement

Table 28
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Complexities Encountered in Parental Involvement and the Strategies Employed in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom

Complexities on Parental Involvement and the following Strategies Employed in Teaching English in a Multilingual Classroom	Probability of r	Remarks
Code-switching	0.9660	Not Significant
Translation	0.5899	Not Significant
Feedback	0.3749	Not Significant
Collaboration	0.5670	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant relationship between the complexities encountered in parental involvement and the strategies employed in teaching English in a multilingual classroom are disclosed in Table 28. It is evident from the results that the P-values of r are greater than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is no significant relationship between the complexities encountered in parental involvement and the strategies employed in teaching English in a multilingual classroom. It states that the code-switching, translation, feedback, and collaboration strategies used by the teachers in teaching English in a multilingual classroom do not significantly affect the complexities they encounter in parental involvement.

The findings above are similar to the study by Chavez et al. (2023), which examined teachers' perspectives on parental involvement for Spanish-speaking English learners. The findings indicated that while teachers employed various strategies to engage parents, challenges persisted due to cultural and linguistic differences.

Conclusions

This study concludes that teachers in multilingual classrooms face various complexities, with learners' interest and motivation being the most significant challenge, followed by parental involvement, learners' proficiency, teaching resources, and communication skills. To address these, teachers primarily use strategies such as code-switching, translation, and feedback, while collaboration is the least employed strategy. However, the effectiveness of these strategies varies—translation and feedback help with learners' proficiency, and collaboration addresses communication skills and teaching resources, but no strategy significantly impact learner's interest and motivation or parental involvement. Additionally, teachers' experiences on these complexities differ based on sex, age, highest educational attainment, grade level handled, and school size.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were made.

1. Given that learners' interest and motivation were identified as the most significant complexity, school administrators should develop faculty training programs focused on student engagement strategies in multilingual classrooms and allocate funds for contextualized instructional materials. Administrators should also encourage teachers to integrate collaborative learning approaches, as the study found this strategy to be effective in improving communication skills.
2. DepEd Officials should provide training on translation and code-switching to help learners gradually improve their English skills without becoming too dependent on these methods. Since feedback helps students learn better, teachers should be trained to give clear and useful feedback. Collaboration should also be encouraged to improve communication skills and make better use of teaching resources.
3. Since learners' interest and motivation are the biggest complexity, yet translation and code-switching are the most used strategies, teachers must balance their approach. Teachers should gradually reduce translation and code-switching as students become more confident in English.
4. Learners should develop independence in learning English by engaging in interactive activities, practicing daily conversations, and using educational resources beyond translation and code-switching.
5. Parents should actively support your child's English learning by encouraging reading, practicing conversations at home, and participating in school language programs to strengthen their confidence and skills.
6. For the researcher, it is recommended to explore additional strategies that can effectively enhance learners' interest and motivation, as this was identified as the most significant challenge. Since translation and code-switching are the most used strategies but may lead to student dependency, the researcher should investigate alternative instructional approaches that promote independent learning.
7. For future researchers, they may conduct experimental studies to determine the long-term effects of translation and code-switching on learners' English proficiency and motivation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles governing educational research. Prior to the conduct of the study, permission was formally secured from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan through appropriate official channels. Coordination was likewise made with the respective school heads of the selected schools before the administration of the research instrument. The researcher ensured that all respondents were properly informed about the purpose and nature of the study and that their participation was voluntary. The study also observed compliance with the Data Privacy Act in handling the respondents' demographic information and questionnaire responses. All data gathered were treated with strict

confidentiality and were used solely for academic and research purposes. The identities of the respondents were protected, and the information collected was analyzed and presented with honesty, accuracy, and integrity. No participant was forced or coerced to take part in the study, and respect for the rights, welfare, and dignity of all respondents was upheld throughout the research process.

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